

Nembe and Kalabari-Ijo City States Relations in the 19th and 20th Centuries: A Critical Reflection of Intergroup Dynamics in Nigeria

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Abstract

The Nembe is flanked by Kalabari on the east, of which, both are of the Ijo stock. They established varied dimensions of relations between them in the Niger Delta for centuries that, cover all the spheres of human endeavour known to the people such as economic, socio-cultural, war, political, diplomacy among others that bond the neighbours together. However, the central argument in this paper is that, despite their Ijoid ancestry, each exploited its advantageous position at different times consolidate and vigorously pursued its foreign policy, sometimes at the detriment of the other, and strike the balance to forestall the existing balance of power in the region like Europeans in the 19th Century. It is therefore highlighted that the European overseas trade and politics provided the incendiary material that sparked-off wars between them, and their implications on intergroup relations were mainly harvested in contemporary Nigeria. In order to buttress this point, the paper relied on the use of primary and secondary sources of data collection for analysis to unravel the richness and variety of the linkages established between them in the 19th and 20th centuries.

Keywords: *City States, Intergroup Relations, Trade, Politics, War and Diplomacy.*

Background

The Nembe and Kalabari relations was predicated on the fact that no group is entirely self-sufficient. They engaged themselves in different ways. However, Professor Alagoa has seamlessly demonstrated the Ijoid origins of both groups despite contrary views expressed by Dike and Jones among others scholars, looking at the directions of Igbo, Benin, Ile Ife etc which glaringly undermined the Ijo factor, and the internal dynamics orchestrated by environmental and long distance trade that propelled the process. As both the Nembe and Kalabari oral traditions eloquently supported central delta origins of their ancestor founders from Obiama and Ogobiri-Igbedi creek region of the Wilberforce Island, all in Bayelsa State, especially Kalabari moved northwards to Amafa before finally settled at Elem-Kalabari (Old Shipping) in the Delta. In fact the both dialects has been classified under the dialect cluster spoken in Eastern Ijo which themselves belong to the Ijo language group.¹

Available evidence suggested there was no account of war between them before the 19th century. Following the incessant state of warfare with Bonny and Okrika in the 18th century and courted the friendship of Nembe. In light of that, Nembe maintained good relations with Kalabari. It is also a clear indication, Nembe was then using the sea ports of Bonny and Kalabari as outlets in the overseas trade; as the Nembe sea ports did not host frequently European merchant ships at the time. This is not to lose the fact, Alagoa however contends that, Nembe fought against Kalabari-speaking communities of Bile, and Kula. But according to this account, the two towns appear then independent of Kalabari's suzerainty, hence acted independently. It went further to assert, the war between Ikata of Nembe and Jike of Bile is indeed, a classic example of a punitive action undertaken to curb the excesses of entrepot communities.²

Again, Alagoa while writing about their relations asserts the friendship between the Nembe and Kalabari disappeared in the mid-19th century as they began to exploit new palm oil markets northwest wards in the Orashi River region, an area claimed by Nembe as her exclusive commercial preserve. They accordingly clashed following the desire to acquire new palm oil markets.³ Though expectedly, Nembe friendship with Bonny, as with Okrika, is usually explained by kinship and religious ties as Ikuba and Ogidiga deities are brothers, hence, is taboo to wage war against the other. The feeling of brotherhood was greatly strengthened by the distance between them, and therefore fought no war. Following this, Nembe and her eastern allies of Bonny and Okrika always fought against Kalabari as a common enemy in the 19th century.

This paper examined the many-sided relations established between the Nembe and Kalabari in the 19th and 20th centuries to showcase the richness and variety of the linkages; variety is indeed the chief characteristic of their relations. This is so because, the peoples under survey do, however, have many features in common. Therefore, for comprehensive analysis of finds and re-examination the paper is segmented into three major historical epochs namely; pre-colonial, colonial, and post-colonial eras in order to vehemently articulate the established relations between them.

Relations During the Pre-Colonial Era

As aforementioned, in the first two decades of the 19th century Kalabari and Bonny was the market places of Nembe overseas trade. This scenario changed from the third decade when

the British Navy effectively policed the coast of Bonny and Kalabari to suppress the slave trade in the region. Then Nembe was transformed into a new haven of the trade in human merchandise. She utilized what providence and trade vagaries bestowed her. Consequently, Bonny, Okrika, and Kalabari extended trade and sold slaves at Nembe. Most of her eastern neighbours, especially Kalabari established a new partnership with Nembe during this period.

Also, the period between 1830 and 1850 Eferibo writes saw an increased demand for palm oil and price like that, Bonny and Kalabari were prominent suppliers. However, Nembe, Lagos, Itsekiri as well as the Royal Niger Company after the 1850s became major players of palm produce trade. And by the Nembe-British Treaty of 1856, she stopped smuggling slaves to Portugal and other Latin American nations. Following the treaty, Nembe began to exploit palm oil markets in the Orashi River and Oguta lake region. He further emphasized that the three new competitors entry into the palm oil trade aggravated the already violent trade in the Niger Delta. Despite the violence, each state developed new palm oil markets further afield, especially into its neighbour trading spheres; coupled with the challenge of dealing with entrepot communities, which sought to benefit in the trade.⁴

Overtime resulting from monopolistic tendency each of them sought to exclude its rival state from doing business in markets it wished to make its own. On this accounts Jones reported they also extended their trade empire or economic region at the rival's expense, not to ply trade with customers from other states except its middlemen. Apparently before the palm oil or legitimate trade, the region was a free trade zone for both states but arising from the competitive element built into the trade both sides laid claim on the region. Thus, there were series of clashes between Nembe and Kalabari on one hand and Kalabari, Okrika and Bonny on the other hand. Therefore, the commercial rivalries of the earlier period changed to commercial wars between them. This is aptly captured by Jones that;

The kalabari developed new markets on the Sombreiro River which was fast flowing and difficult to navigate above Degema, but their main expansion was at the expense of Nembe into that part of the delta referred to in the records as long Brass or Eganny, an area marginal to Kalabari and Nembe Bonny developed the Ibo and Ogoni oil markets on the mainland bordering Okrika and sought to expand at Kalabari

*expense by encouraging Okrika to lay claim to the 'Obiatoru' markets on the new Calabar River, and by asserting ancient rights to trade in the Sombreiro and lower Niger Markets.*⁵

The above clearly suggests that the trade rivalries of the period ignited the series of wars fought between them in the 19th century. As the Kalabari which strategically occupied the Sombreiro River, which is the bridge between Nembe and her eastern allies posed major threat to free trade in the region. Following this drastic measure was taken to ensure that trade was not strangled by Kalabari, and each time she did so, she was blockade upstream by Nembe. The commercial rivalry triggered war between them. Again, Jones remarked; "it is however, certain that the Brass (Nembe) people have been the victors. In one day they dropped it is said three canoes containing thirty of their enemies and have altogether captured or killed hundred of the new Calabar men who can hardly show a skull in return."⁶ Corroboratively Webster and Boahen wrote that Kalabari was being battered at war by her more powerful rivals, lamented thus; Elem-Kalabari was the first victim of the commercial struggle of the 1880s. The state was already exhausted in wars fought to preserve its trading empire against its powerful neighbours, Bonny and Brass, and by the necessity of transporting oil in convoys escorted by war canoes.⁷

On account of this Alagoa and Okorobia reports that, on realizing the great harm the war was causing his state, king Abi Amakiri decided to sue for peace through Consul Hopkins in 1871. According to this account, the parties were accordingly invited to Brass on the 21st of November 1871 to sign a perpetual treaty of peace under the mediation of the British government represented by Consul David Hopkins. They went further to state that, the treaty among other things, looked into territorial claims of the two parties and adjudicated that "in ascending the Engene or Orashi River from the Sombreiro-Ologolo creek, as far as to Oguta, all the markets on the left bank belonged to the Nembe, all those on the right bank belonged to Kalabari". As soon as the treaty was signed, the kings shook hands and drank wine together as friends and dispersed.⁸

Also, in 1898, however, the already settled boundary issue was re-opened by Kalabari. The matter was brought before the Consul General, Captain Gallway, who on the 31st of October 1898 again decided at Degema that the Engene River belonged entirely to the Nembe people and upheld the judgement posited earlier by Consul David Hopkins in 1871.

The point of interest in this account is not so much the Nembe victory as it was of the spirit of diplomacy by the states of co-existence in the Niger Delta of Nigeria.

Furthermore, the relationship between Nembe and Kalabari tends to show that despite accounts of many open hostilities there were also periods of trade, politics, diplomacy as well as peaceful co-existence. As Waibinte Wariboko observed that after Nembe fought against the forces of imperialism (Royal Niger Company) in 1895 and was defeated, Kalabari extended financial assistance to Nembe. Commenting on the amiable relationship that existed between them, he therefore wrote; “King Princewill Amachree of New Calabar (Kalabari) according to the records did send 200 cases of gin to the King of Nembe (Brass) Fredrick William Koko after their eventual defeat by the Royal Niger Company in 1895”.⁹ It was a masterpiece of true friendship, brotherhood and diplomacy, however, the gesture did not last long as event in their relations brilliantly showed.

All of these events demonstrated one fundamental similarity in them, as victims of the harsh monopoly of the Royal Niger Company in the lower Niger dealt with the British during the transition to colonial rule. At the height of their respective frustration, both states decided on military confrontation. However, Kalabari was restrained by Nembe's defeat, was spared retribution. The interesting point here is that unlike Nembe, Kalabari survived into the twentieth century as a vital middleman after the political demise of company rule in 1900.¹⁰

Relations During the Colonial Era

The Nembe-British war of 1895 was a game-changer of sort not only in Nembe history, but also in the historical development of Nigeria. It generated a series of events and served as catalyst to accelerate the establishment of the colonial rule in Nigeria. This war is perhaps, one event that best illustrates the demise of Nembe middleman as elsewhere in the Delta region except for the Opobo and Kalabari, as aforementioned above. The firm establishment of colonial rule in Nigeria, which for administrative exigencies put strain on their relations with the re-organization of protectorates, provinces, and divisions etc. as they were balkanized for this purpose every now and then which served its intends in 1900, 1906, and 1914 and so on. Essentially therefore, the key point to make is that the metamorphoses of British policies actually affected the relationship of the two states as the colonial era wore on.

For instance, Eferebo recorded an incidence that after the Akassa war of 1895 with the British agent of imperialism, the Nembe export-import (middleman) trade dedined. He basically ascribed the twin factors of the silting of the Brass River and inland movement or penetration of traders to the areas of produce as the major reasons for it. According to him, due to the colonial government policy in 1920 the Nembe port was shut, and so disposed her trade goods at Abonnema (in kalabari). He further remarked that it was an era of the creation of a new middleman monopoly as events in their relationship highlighted.¹¹

In the palm produe trade, for example, Nembe traders were being subjected to trade on the terms imposed by the Kalabari middlemen. On the 5th of November 1902, the high commissioner of the Niger Coast Protectorateas reported that;

I was informed by the Brass (Nembe) cheifs, that their boys going to trade in the new Calabar(Kalabari) districts are prevented by the Abonnema (Kalabari) chiefs from preceeding beyond Abonnema town to the actual producing market so that in effect Abonnema was createdamiddleman market and the Brass men are compelled to purchase there. The Brass men have also.....been buying up a lot of bad kernels from the new calabar men,which the latter would not dispose of locally.¹²

The commercial dominance of Kalabari over Nembe as a middleman was glaring in the 20th century. It was howevr more conspicuous at the commercial centers of Kregeni, Omoku and Oguta lake region that was Nembe spheres of influence, that was wrested from them by the Royal Niger company. But perhaps, the greater available evidence to corroborate the Nembe claimed of that region was adduced by Professor Nzimiro; while writing about the farm settlements in Oguta which was associated with the slaves and other bonded persons in the pre-colonial times was forthcoming, his words, "this is particularly revealing of the hardship the wage labourers endured because Oguta had enough fish, and the Nembe fish traders had outposts in Oguta ". He quickly added "the generally poor condition of these labourers is reflected in the attitude which is still held towards Igbo hinterland dwellers by the Oguta people. It explains the general Oguta disdain "food of the Igbo people".¹³

Of significance was the revocation of the Royal Niger Company's charter in 1900. Following this, the Nembe and Kalabari middlemen traders relocated into the lower Niger to resume their cut-throat commercial ventures as usual. By 1907, available evidence

showed that Kalabari had squashed Nembe traders in the Orashi region. Also, in 1913 a similar case was reported about by Mr. J.M. Pollen, the Acting District Officer of Owerri Province. "There is a large New Calabar (Kalabari) trading colony at Oguta with various New Calabar Chiefs often resident. They are competitors on trade with the Ogutans". And again, it was reported in 1918 that "... the Brass people have now decided to renew hostilities by driving out the New Calabar traders from Oguta, claiming that they were the original traders there and have been ousted by the New Calabars".¹⁴

And, as though these developments were not enough problems for the Kalabari, its trading colony at Oguta came to be what Waibinte Wariboko referred to as "Indian Summer" survived into the forth decades of the 20th century as a viable middleman for the export-import trade in the lower Niger. This was so evident as providence paved way for the Kalabari a new era of prosperity during which, she enjoyed more or less uninterrupted monopoly in the lower Niger region.¹⁵

Again, Wabinte Wariboko has, for instance, reported that in 1934, quoting the Assistant District Officer Owerri Division that "there are several trading settlements in the South side of Oguta Lake, chief among which is the New Calabar settlement composed chiefly of wealthy traders from Abomema, their labourers and we therefore not that the evidence showed even in the 1930s the middlemen of the Eastern Delta prospered as against the study of Professor Nwabughugu that claimed the demise of the middleman trade. According to this study, 1916 to 1930 was "a period of their (middlemen) elimination from an effective big trading role". Interestingly as Wabinte Wariboko observe "this interpretaton is more accurate for the middlemen for Bonny and Nembe (Brass) than for those of New Calabar (Kalabari) and Opobo in the Niger Delta".¹⁶

We therefore note that the evidence showed even in the 1930s the middleman of the Eastern Delta prospered as against the study of Professor Nwabughugu that claimed the demise of the middleman trade. According to this study, 1916 to 1930 was " a period of their (middleman) elimination from an effective big trading role". And as Wabinte Wariboko observe " this interpretation is more accurate for the middlemen of Bonny and Nembe than for those of the New Calabar (Kalabari) and Opobo in the Niger Delta."¹⁷

One interesting feature of their relationship is that war had not created any barrier between them. War in this context is diplomacy by another means, as a principal agent through

which new cultural ideas cross-fertilized relations. This is so because, after wars are fought and peaceful settlements inter-marriage followed to cement peaceful co-existence between rivals. This form of inter-state marriages encouraged linguistic or cultural exchanges. Eferebo, for example, reported that Ekine or Sekiapu masquerade dance society was first established in Kalabari. According to this report, it was later introduced by Nembe through the instrumentality of Prince Orugbani, son of King Jacket Mein (Nembe), whose mother is from Kalabari. He however submitted that Nembe spread Ekine dance among other places as far as Ijebu-Ode in Yorubaland.¹⁸

Corroboratively, Professor Robin Horton has identified the popularity of the Ekine masquerade society among the Ijebu towns as one of the cultural impact of the Eastern Delta States on their neighbours. He aptly remarked that "the Ekine is an Eastern Delta water spirit masquerade society, up to this day, the Ijebu sing the ritual songs of Ekine; in a language which appears to be a degenerated form of Ijo".¹⁹ It should be emphasized here the cultural impact of the Kalabari dialect on the Nembe was fascinatingly great. As the Kalabari seats on the Sombreiro River, the highway of the overseas trade on one hand and the long distance trade among the Eastern Delta States on the other; therefore, for Nembe to survive and mingle freely on the highway, the Kalabari dialect was sine qua non.

Writing on the relationship between the Nembe and Kalabari, Eferebo has identified the importance of the Kalabari dialect on the Nembe dialect speakers into the last decades of the 20th century. He therefore states that;

The city states of Nembe and Kalabari, no doubt, had a number of social contacts and interactions expressed mostly in dialect, songs and dances. The social activities that had transpired between the two groups over the years even to recent times are numerous. The Kalabari dialect of the Ijo language according to many Nembe traditional accounts, exercised much influence on the singing and dancing in Nembe. Chief O.A.J. Yousuo (Chief Priest of Ogidiga) confirmed that traditional songs in Nembe were said to have been composed in Kalabari. It was said that up to the 1980s, songs composed in Kalabari dialect were used for both cultural (juju festivals) and social gatherings. Though the first recorded Nembe

*dialect songs came to light in the 1950s through the instrumentality, dynamic, and visionary ideas of Chief O.A.J. Yousuo, the originator of Nembe dialect songs.*²⁰

He went further to say that parents of Nembe preferred to christen children in the Kalabari dialect. Few examples surface here (i.e) Tamuno, Iboromo, Ibiene etc. While others are given Nembe colouration for example, Iyozu corrected to Inodu aptly demonstrated the influence of Kalabari, as it became a second dialect of Nembe speakers as we have showed.

The introduction of 1946 and 1954 constitutions as well as the policies of colonial Nigeria raised cold feet in their relations as the administration source to generate finance, and to effectively administer the areas fishing tax was introduced. There arose also jurisdiction problems between Brass and Degema Districts, as they came to be known during the colonial era. Arising from the above issues among others several administrative orders were put in place especially in 1944 and 1954 respectively, where an artificial boundary was created for them at Santa Barbara River, for administrative purposes. The orders also divided the river into east and west. This exercise gave the east bank to Kalabari while the west bank to Nembe.

The orders were vehemently challenged by the Nembe citing the 1871 treaty between the two parties with Consul David Hopkins, and the 1898 arbitration of Captain Gallway. The boundary was fixed at the Sombreiro River (Agudatoru) as contained in the 1871 Nembe-Kalabari treaty of perpetual peace aforementioned in this paper subsequently. We note however that the administrative boundary at the Santa Barbara River was only for administrative purposes and does not confer title to any one became a major source of conflict that was mainly harvested as their contemporary relations tends to show.²¹ We turn to the contemporary or post-colonial relations in the next segment.

Relations During the Post - Colonial Era

The post-colonial era took a different dimension as they came to acknowledge or realize the nonchalant attitude of the government in the relations between them. Though in 1962, the Kalabari people instituted a law suit against Nembe, claiming among others 22 communities, all on the west bank of the Santa Barbara River. Nembe also filed its statement of defence. But realizing the futility of their claims, the Kalabari people failed to

prosecute the case further. The important point to note is that, the civil war broke out on 4 July 1967, five years, after the Kalabari people filed their summons. The civil war cannot therefore be given as an excuse for their failure to prosecute the case.²²

Eferebo, for example adduced that, although the above court case, was discontinued after the war, but however the discontent it has created continued to hunt them. It came to a whole in 1967 when Rivers State was created, and a maiden map was drawn in 1970 in which most of the Nembe communities were drafted under Degema Division. Nembe protested the viability of the map and claimed for example the Oluasiri and Obioku cluster of communities to be transferd to their original Brass Division. The issue became more contentious, when Akuku Toru Local Government Area was created in 1991, out of the parent Degema. Again, ceding the Oluasiri and Obioku Cluster of communities in Brass local Government Area on the west bank of the Santa Barbara River to constitute the newly created Akuku Toru.²³

What also comounded relations among other issues was the discovery of petroleum and gas in the disputed area (between Santa Barbara and San Bartholomew Rivers). The discoveries also fanned the flames of disharmony between them that had lingered since the creation of Rivers State. Arising from the payment of royalties to host communities by the oil companies, as it is to be expected, each of the parties laid claim and sought to be recognized as landlord in order to receive royalties. The possibility of open clashes became inevitable. This is coupled with the customary collection of rent from tenants that ply their trade. The result is that each encroached on others spheres and indulge in nefarious activities in the disputed area. This usually culminated into fighting between the rivals which often times resulted into open clashes.²⁴

Again, Eferebo recorded an incident on 12 December, 1993, that Kalabari chiefs came to collect rent at Akannanga (or Owukubu) fishing settlements. All the settlements are on the west bank of Santa Barbara River, defined by the administrative orders of 1944 and 1954; where the Kalabari has no legal right to do so. Therefore, resident quickly mobilize to forestall the rent collection, shortly fighting ensued between them. Accordingly, any step undertaken by the parties on the disputed area is interpreted as an aggression. He quickly added, it was in the midst of fear and suspicion that the incidence of Thursday, 3 February 1994 when four speed boats with passages travelling from Port Harcourt to Nembe were

attacked and killed. The boats were attacked at 90km, near Kampala village by an unidentified armed men, which Nembe suspected to be Kalabari. The consequence was the out break of war between Nembe and Kalabari. According to this account, it was the prompt action of the then military administration that ended the war with laughable consequences.²⁵

The lessons learnt was that before the war Kalabari chiefs undertook a diplomatic mission to Nembe in order to resolve all outstanding matters through dialogue. Following this fine diplomacy, Nembe also reprocated. They both blamed government for all their misfortunes. Shortly after wards, the Nembe chiefs openly alleged the previous attack on Kalabari people, casting aspersions on them. The Kalabari chiefs swiftly stated their innocence, and as such, retaliated and also accused her rival as being the one responsible for all the atrocities that had befallen them.²⁶

Arguably the other potent sources of conflict between them was and is that, the political economy of the peoples' (Nembe and Kalabari) are fishing and trading due to environmental factors. Fishing being the main stay of the people, and therefore, criss cross each other's territory in search of better fishing grounds. On the whole, the foudnation of settlements (Borikiri) to conduct their activities, especially the pelagic fish (sardine) like the herring family (afaru or afare in both dialects) are migratory. Following this they settled in each others territory and draw their home authority or government into the area as source of revenue collection brought disharmony between them as aforementioned earlier in the paper.

As matters arising from the issues calibrated in the paper apparently showed no defined boundary between the Nembe and Kalabari. Thus, as noted earlier, was the colonial administration's division into provinces, divisions, districts etc for administrative purposes without any regard for the traditional boundaries. The result was and is the near crisis situation of the many boundary disputes among communities/groups especially the Nembe and Kalabari which translates into Bayelsa and Rivers States boundary. The opportunity to correct these mistakes offered itself in 1949 with the establishment of the Justice G.G. Robonson's Commission of Inquiry by the Government into the Bonny, Okirka and Kalabari dispute. Even the more recent Justice Akere's Judicial Commission of Inquiry occasioned by the Rivers State Government in 1993; aside declaring the disputed area as a

"buffer zone" and fifty fifty sharing clause nothing tangible happened.²⁷ So also the Federal boundary commission too has not put the matter to rest.

Meanwhile the Nembe and Kalabari have learned to live with the endemic problem, as they evolved appropriate measures to overcome it. They chose to live in peace as government seemed to have chosen the path of "might is right" in this regard. They live in relative peace despite the challenges; certainly utilized hinge sight. Following this attitudinal change. The previous Nembe and Kalabari prejudices fell to the background as a result of the "Kaima Declaration" in 1998 by Ijaw Youths Council at Kaima. The Kaima declaration among other things provided the various Ijo (Ijaw) clans incendiary material to protest their long neglect of the federal government despite the huge contribution of the region to the economy. The application of the fifty/fifty sharing formula recommended by the Akere's commission in 1993, for the disputed area between them became a subtle diplomacy of sort for peaceful co-existence.

The above situation can better be explained by Elder Esua Ameri when he opined "this all inclusive arrangement made the contending parties to follow the path of mutual co-existence. It was through this process that modalities were worked out to engender a peaceful environment the Liquefied Natural Gas project at Oluasiri (erroneously called Soku) was managed". Though he added that the LNG is in Oluasiri (cluster of Nembe towns) but to avoid bloodshed with our Kalabari neighbours we all agreed to work together and relied on the fifty/fifty arrangement as recommended by Akere's commission pending when government will say otherwise.²⁸

Accordingly, the fifty/fifty sharing arrangement brought the two foes together, which prepared them for greater challenges in the years ahead. When it came finally in the year 2000 AD they were adequately equipped to overcome these challenges as they engaged in a new dispensation of relationship. Therefore, during the era of Niger Delta militancy against the Nigerian government as defined by the "Kaima Declaration", it was organized like a family business. This is not to suggest that there were not challenges but they were surmountable, and as such, relations between them has been peaceful.

Concluding Remarks

In the foregoing historical journey thus far, we have attempted to showcase in this paper the richness and variety of the linkages established between the Nembe and Kalabari Ijo city

states in the 19th and 20th centuries, in Nigeria's geographical space through challenging but evolving epochs of history. This paper has, therefore, argued with greater vehemence that despite the incidences of war and warfare perpetrated between the neighbours, it does not in anyway infringed on the social, cultural, political, economic and diplomatic relations established between them; as the wars boomed large in the oral account of the people.

We however note that the incendiary germinated and fertilized during the colonial era when it established administrative orders 1944, 1952, and 1954, which though fixed administrative boundaries between Nembe (Brass Division) and Kalabari (Degema Division) at the Santa Barbara River, that was only for administrative purposes and does not confer title to anyone; was harvested in the post-colonial era which become the dagger each use against the other's throat. And, more important relations has been peaceful between them.

Endnotes

¹ E. E. Efero and K. Willaiamson, *Langauages*, in *Land and People of Nigeria Rivers State*, ed. E. J. Alagoa and T. N. Tekena, Port Harcourt: Riverside Communication, 1989, pp.43-44

² E. J. Alagoa, "The Niger Delta States and their Neighbours in 1800", *The History of West Africa Vol. 1*, Second Edition, ed. F. J. A. Ajayi and M. Crowder, New York: Longman Group Ltd, 1976, p.353

³ E. J. Alagoa, "The Eastern Niger Delta and the Hinterland in the 19th Century", in *Groundwork of Nigerian History*, Ibadan: Heinemann Educational Books Ltd, 1980, p.251

⁴ I. Efero, "Nembe and Her Neighbours, 1800-2008", An Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Department of History and Diplomatic Studies, Faculty of Humanities, University of Port Harcourt, 2013, p.114

⁵ G. I. Jones, *The Trading Status of the Oil Rivers: A Study of Political Development in Eastern Nigeria*, London: Oxford University Press, p.146

⁶ *Ibid*, p.148

⁷ J. B. Webster and A. A. Boahen (1967 quoted) in Efero, "Nembe and Her Neighbours", p.118

⁸ E. J. Alagoa and A. M. Okorobia, *Nembe Se Congress: A Study of the United Approach to Development in Nembe Se*, Port Harcourt: Onyome Research Publications, p.43

⁹ W. Wariboko, "New Calabar Middlemen, Her Majesty's Consuls, and British Traders in the late Nineteenth Century. Niger Delta During the Era of New Imperialism", in *The Aftermath of Slavery: Transition and Transformation in Southeastern Nigeria*, ed. C. J. Okorieh and F. J. Kolapo, New York: African World Press, 2007, p.32

¹⁰ I. Efero, "Nembe and Her Neighbours", p.123

¹¹ *Ibid*, p.125

¹² Wariboko, "New Calabar Middlemen", p.34

¹³ I. Nzimiro (1971 quoted) in A. A. Agorua, *The Oguta Middleman: A Study in Socio-Economic History*, Lagos: Arthill Publishers Ltd, 2015, p.36

¹⁴ Wariboko, "New Calabar Middlemen" pp34-35

¹⁵ Ibid, 35

¹⁶ Opcit

¹⁷ I. Eferebo, "A Comparative Study of the Nembe and Kalabari Peoples, 1900-1995, An Unpublished Bachelor of Education & History Project, Development of History, Faculty of Arts, University of Ibadan, 1996, p.34

¹⁸ Robin Horton. "The Economy of Ife c A.D. 900-1700", in *The Cradle of a Race: Ife from the Beginning to 1980*, ed. I. A. Akinjogbin, Lagos: Sunray Publications, 1992, p.128

¹⁹ Eferebo, "A Comparative Study of the Nembe and Kalabari Peoples", pp36-37

²⁰ Adaye Orugbani Professor, Oral Interview conducted during my Doctoral fieldwork at Abormema, Rivers State on 4/6/2011

²¹ Eferebo, "Nembe and Her Neighbours", p.140. See also, A. M. Okorobia, *An Introduction to Opu-Nembe: The Land and People of Eastern Nembe*, Port Harcourt: Niger Delta Heritage Centre, 2014, p.77

²² Eferebo, "A Comparative Study of the Nembe and Kalabari Peoples", p.66

²³ Solomon, D. Dambo Chief, Oral Interview conducted during my Doctoral fieldwork at Port Harcourt on 26/11/2011

²⁴ Eferebo, "A Comparative Study" p.68

²⁵ Daily Sunray Newspaper, Thursday 8, 1994, pp.10-11

²⁶ P. B. Akere, "Conclusions of the Government of Rivers State on the Report of the Judicial Commission of Inquiry into the Disturbances/Conflicts between Akuku-Toru and Brass Local Government Areas of Rivers State", Port Harcourt: The Government Printing Press, 1993, pp.8-9

²⁷ Eferebo, "Nembe and Her Neighbours", pp.155-156

²⁸ Esua Ameri Elder, Oral Interview conducted during my Doctoral fieldwork at Oluasiri, Nembe on 16/8/2011